

Values of Teachers in Public Secondary School in General Emilio Aguinaldo National High School Cavite City

Ludovico R. Resuello, Jr. ¹
1 – Palaris College
ludovico.resuello@deped.gov.ph

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Abstract

This study determined the extent of manifestation of values of the teachers in public secondary schools in Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo Public Secondary Schools, Cavite City along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions. It also looked into the dominant and less dominant value as well as the problems encountered in the manifestation of the above-stated value.

The following are the salient findings of the study: The extent of manifestation of the values of teachers is moderate along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions; There is no significant differences between the perceptions of teachers and students in the effect of manifestation of values of fourth year students; The dominant and less dominant values manifested are as follows: There are no dominant intellectual values, all are less dominant; Two spiritual values, namely, fourth and forging/compassion are dominant. All the others are less dominant; Four (4) economic values, namely, thrift, value of time, hardwork are resourcefulness, are dominant all the other are less dominant; Four (4) economics values, namely thrift, value of time, hardwork and resourcefulness are dominant all the others are less dominant and The degree of seriousness of problems encountered is: Moderate along intellectual values; Moderate along social values; Not serious along spiritual value; Serious along economic values and A plan of action to enhance the manifestation of values of teachers has been proposed.

The conclusion based on the findings of the study are as follows: Most of the values along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions are not yet fully internalized and put into produce by teacher; Both students and teachers have the same perceptions on the extent of manifestation of values of teachers; Most of the values along the individual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions are not fully evident in the behavior and conduct of teachers; The seriousness of the problems hampers the manifestation of the values of teachers along all dimensions and A proposed plan the enhance the manifestation and internalization of values of teacher has been formulated.

Keywords: *teacher values, intellectual values, social values, spiritual values, economic values, public secondary school, General Emilio Aguinaldo National High School, Cavite City, values manifestation, educational management*

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM

Rationale

When we think of values, we think of what is important to us in our lives (e.g. security, independence, wisdom, success, kindness, pleasure). Each of us hold numerous values with varying degrees of importance. A particular value may be very important to one person but unimportant to another.

Values are beliefs. But they are beliefs tied inextricably to emotion, not objective, cold ideas. They are motivational contrasts which are desirable goals people strive to attain. They transcend specific actions and situations. They are abstract goals. The abstract nature of values distinguishes them from concepts like norms and attitudes which actually refer to specific actions, objects, or situations. They guide the selection or evaluation of actions, policies, people and events. Values serve as standards or criteria. They are ordered by importance relative to one another. People's values form an ordered system of value priorities that characterize them as individuals. (Morris, 2005).

In order to coordinate with others in the pursuit of the goals that are important to them, groups and individuals represent these requirements cognitively as specific values about which they communicate. These values are derived from the three universal requirements of the human conditions which are needs of the individuals, as biological organism requisites of coordinated social interaction, and survival and welfare needs of the group.

According to Schwartz (2012) values are derived from the prerequisites of interactions and of group survival. For interaction to proceed smoothly and for groups to maintain themselves, individuals must restrain impulses and inhibit actions that might hurt others. A self-direction value is derived from organismic needs for mastery, from the interaction needs for mastery and form the interaction requirements of autonomy and independence.

People's values vary from one another. There are some people who value integrity, honor and dignity; others value material, spiritual, social and intellectual values. Speaking of social values and organization, the great majority of the Philippine population is bound together by common values, and common religion. It is characterized by many positive traits among which are strong religious faith, respect for authority, and high regard for self-esteem and smooth interpersonal relationship.

In this research, the researcher was inspired to investigate the values of fourth year high school students along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic values. Intellectual values challenge the students to exhibit courage in sharing their beautiful ideas and insights on certain things or issues to help others improve themselves and society. They may instill in them the wide range of understanding the situation and condition of others during events of calamities and the solutions of any problem of man and society. It may mean intellectual integrity, having firm-mindedness while respecting the opinion of others and acceptance of them.

Social values deal with bonds of kinship, social affiliation and concern with one another.

It may be the expression or manifestation of cooperation with fellow students, admiration of the good things from others. It may also mean open communication as internalized in their day to day interaction of being conforming and behave in the spirit of friendship, honesty, self reliance and sincerity. These comprise the social values of the students that are manifested by them as social beings.

Garlikov (2013) averred that spiritual values are manifested when experiencing awe, wonder and mystery. It is an opportunity to reflect on lie's fundamental questions and a search for meaning and purpose, for the development of spirit, soul, personality and character. It is internalized through recognizing the worth of others and gaining the ability to build up relationships with others using feeling and emotions.

The economic values of the students are expressed in terms of proper valuing, using and saving time for truthful activities. The practice of thrift, quality of choices on goods and other products and willingness to pay an obligation as well as conservative buying and spending within ones means, conservation and valuing hard work are some economic values that the students manifest in life.

This study intended to identify the extent manifestation of the above-state values in the daily lives of students. The researcher, as a high school teachers, observed and noted that sometimes the students fail to internalize intellectual values particularly during the discussion time when they laugh at the opinion, ideas and values of other students. They sometimes hesitate to share their ideas and even clarify some issues to make the point clear. Most of the time, they manifest low quality of thinking skills.

In class, as far as the participation and involvement of the students are concerned, not all participate in doing the task. Socially they lack a sense of cooperation and helpfulness. In a sense, it can be said that their social values are low or poorly internalized. These affect the development of social skills and personal qualities necessary for playing an effective role in group or society and skills essential for successful relationship.

Spiritually speaking, the students have poor development of values, principles and beliefs which may or may not be religious and understanding the beliefs of others. They lack the ability to recognize the worth of others and to gain the ability to build up relationship with others.

The above-stated situations, have motivated the researcher to conduct this study. As a teacher, it is her desire to identify the extent of manifestation of the values of fourth year students and on the basis of the findings, propose measures to develop in the students, the right and correct value system.

Theoretical Framework

This research is based on the theory of Chippendale (2014) that describe the links between, values, morals ethics and principles. It explains the code of behavior and values. If we know the values a person holds, we will have a general idea of what they want to do in their life. For example if a person's highest priority value is achievement / success we would expect them to be striving towards one or more goals and doing whatever they can do to achieve them. Likewise, if a person's highest priority value is knowledge, we would expect them to be in an

intellectual, social, spiritual perspective.

So there is a link between values and the general category of activities the person would be expected to be involved in because of the priority values he has.

This is represented in figure 1.

We filter what we “see” through our values

The theory is very applicable to the investigation on values of the fourth year high school students which are intellectual, social, spiritual and economic values. Their values determine the behavior they manifest and affect their acts or decisions. As they filter their values, knowing a person’s value gives one general idea as to what activities are important to them.

Conceptual Framework

The values of the fourth year students in public secondary schools in Malasiqui, Pangasinan are manifested in their day to day living. They manifest them in classes, homes, other occasions and instances as they relate with others. In school, fourth years students manifest certain kinds of values like, intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions. They practice these in different levels in different situations and occasions.

The conceptual framework of the study is anchored on the paradigm illustration in input-process-output scheme.

The input box contains the extent of manifestation of values of the fourth year students as perceived by themselves and their teachers, the dominant and less dominant values manifested by them and the degree of the seriousness of the problems encountered in the manifestation of values.

The second box which is the process contains the analysis of findings as the following: extent of the manifestation of values by the student; dominant and less dominant values manifested; the degree of seriousness of the problems met, and finally the formulation of the proposed plan of action.

The third box is the output. It contains the proposed plan of action.

Figure 2. Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the extent of manifestation of the values of Public Secondary School in Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School during school year 2026 – 2027.

Specifically it sought to answer to the following questions.

1. What is the extent of manifestation of values of the teachers as perceived by themselves and their Department Head and Coordinator along the following dimensions:
 - a. Intellectual;
 - b. Social;
 - c. Spiritual;
 - d. Economic?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perception of the teachers and the school heads on the extent of manifestation of values of the teachers?
3. What are the dominant and less dominant values manifested?
4. What is the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in the manifestation of values

along the four dimensions?

5. What action plan can be proposed to enhance the values of fourth year high school students?

Research Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between the perception of teachers and their Department Heads.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study dealt with the values of the teachers in public secondary school in General Emilio Aguinaldo National High School for school year 2026 – 2027. It was conducted among the 293 teachers. The variables covered in this study were the extent of manifestation of values of the teachers as perceived by themselves along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic values. The differences between the perceptions of teachers and Department Heads, in as well as their dominant values were covered in the investigation.

The problems encountered by the students in the manifestation of the values along the four dimensions were also considered in the analysis of the data. Finally, the proposed action plan to improve the values of the public secondary school General Emilio Aguinaldo National High School.

Importance of the Study

The results of this study particularly the proposed intensified values education program would be very beneficial to the following people or groups, and other organizations.

Curriculum Planners. The findings of the study will give proper direction to the curriculum planners in deciding some materials in values education so that the students as well as the teachers can work together in developing the whole personality of the students to become more responsible members of the society.

School Administrators. The school administrators can have an idea on how values education program affects the behavior, decision making and attitudes of the students. They can assist the teachers or extend support to the teachers in instilling values and discipline in the school and in the community where they belong.

The students would be able to face the challenge brought about by the problems raised in this study specifically on students related problems, teacher related problems, and environmental related problems.

The proposed values education program can be used by the teachers in sorting out the values of the students and become more firm and stronger in facing some problems in society.

Guidance Counselor. The findings of the study will serve as guides for the guidance counselors to extend services to develop, clarify and strengthen the values of the students.

The Teachers. It could be beneficial for them in a way that they could have a clearer view on what is happening in values education instruction, how the DepEd policies on values are being implemented, the issues on how it should be integrated in various subjects and highlighted in various programs, projects activities of the school. The teachers initiative in identifying the various observable behavior related to values could be directed and enhanced.

Parents. The results of the study will give information to them particular on the different behavioral attitudes and values of their children so that they will be able to perform the role in

enhancing the values of their children along family, peers, environment and any observable behavior.

Students. The values of the students could also be enhanced and redirected and clarified through the able guidance and strategic presentation, activities of the teachers.

Researcher. The findings could give the researcher the concrete picture on how the values of the fourth year students are being manifested. She can make some program or activities, use the action plan to enhance the values of students.

Definition of Terms

The following terms and phrases are defined to shed light on the findings, conclusions and recommendations of the study. They are defined lexically or operationally.

Values education. This refers to the part of school curriculum responsible in processing values formed in the learner.

Integration values. This refers to how values are integrated or observed in subjects like Math, English, Social Science and School Activities.

Implementation of DepEd Policies. This is the manner how the policies on values program are applied or implemented by the DepEd.

Observable behavior. This is the specific manner and attitude observed from the students every time they perform certain tasks and in school, community and society.

Students-related problems. This is the problem met by the students in acquiring the values and their inability to cope up with the challenge they face in their social integration.

Teacher-related problem. it refers to the negative formation of values contribution by the teacher.

Environmental-related values. This is the kind of problem faced by the students in the community or environmental they belong to.

Facilitating Values and Morality. It is the manner of making the acquisition and internalization of values and morality easier and convenient for students.

Skills for values development. It is the ability of students to acquire and develop values and morality.

Values. They refer to the different things or anything that are significant and important to the students or to any person.

Enhancing Values. Refers to the improvement of values of every students or any person as he is engaged in different activities and educational activities.

Environment. This refers to anything that surrounds the individual student which shape the values he has.

Social Values. They refer to belief, conviction and even practices that have a bearing on social affiliation, the welfare of other people showing respect for their and their human personhood as members of society.

Intellectual Values. They refer to beliefs, conviction and even practices that consider the intellectual, rationality and the level of ideas, concepts, and intellectual limitation of other people particularly among fellow students.

Spiritual Values. They refer to beliefs, conviction and even practices that consider the intellectual, rationality and the level of ideas, concepts, and intellectual limitation of other people particularly among fellow students.

Spiritual Values. They refer to beliefs conviction and even practices that consider the

dignity, religion of any person and show generosity compassion, forgiveness, self-sacrifice and low.

Economic Values. They refer to beliefs conviction and even practices that make people thrifty and value the importance of wealth, money, time, and other material human resources.

Related Literature

According to De Leon (2005) social values originate from social organization which generally follows a single pattern, although variations do occur, reflecting the influence of local traditions. Among lowland Christian Filipinos, social organization continues to be marked primarily by personal alliance systems, that is, groupings composed of kin (real and ritual), grantors and recipients of favors, friends, and partners in commercial exchanges.

It is in this social organizations where personal alliance systems are anchored on kinship, beginning with the nuclear family. A Filipino's loyalty goes first to the immediate family; identity is deeply embedded in the web of kinship. It is normative that one owes support, loyalty, and trust to one's close kin and, because kinship is structured bilaterally with afficial as well as consanguineal relatives, one's kin can include quite a large number of people.

According to Kevin Ryan (2008) in his article "Minding the Values in the Curriculum", school, need to take a stronger role in helping the young to discover the good and learn to become individuals of character. While the development of a child's character is clearly not the sole responsibility of the school, historical and legally schools have been major players in this arena. Young people spend much of their lives within school walls. There they will learn, either by chance or design, moral lessons about how people behave.

The above-cited literature and studies have given the researcher a very comprehensive understanding of what values are: the different kinds of values and how said values may be integrated into the curriculum to enable students to form a sound value system. Hence, they have given the researcher a better perspective on how to conduct this study.

Cardwell (2007) said that social interaction which are developed in the bonds of ritual kinship, sealed on any of three ceremonial occasions – baptism, confirmation, and marriage – intensify and extend personal alliances. This mutual kinship system, known as *compadrazgo*, meaning godparenthood or sponsorship, dates back at least to the introduction of Christianity and perhaps earlier. It is a primarily method of extending the group from which one can expect help in the way of favors, such as jobs, loans, or just simple gifts on special occasions. Kevin (2008) said that a dyadic bond-between two individuals – may be formed based on the concept of *utang na loob*. Although it is expected that the debtor will attempt repayment, it is widely recognized that the debt (as in one's obligation to a parent) can never be fully repaid and the obligation can last for generations. Saving another's life, providing employment, or making it possible for another to become educated are "gift" that incur *utang na loob*. Moreover, such gifts initiate a long-term reciprocal interdependency in which the grantor of the favor can expect help from the debtor whenever the needs arises and the debtor can, in turn, ask other favors. Such reciprocal personal alliances have had obvious implications for the society in general and the political system in particular.

According to Haynes (2008) there are three different meanings of spiritual values. The term "spiritual" is often used to described someone who is very religious or who is very devout in his/her worship of God. The "spirit" is often a reference to the holy spirit of God, or, in

Christianity, to the Holy Spirit. The spiritual person is one who is close to God, loves God, always thinks of God, put God first, or who tries to do God's will. It is person whose life, or important aspects of it are, in some way, centered around God.

Or it may mean a relationship between the spirit of God and the spirit of the person, for example that the spiritual person is spiritual because, for example, she/he partakes of the spirit of God", or because "the Holy Spirit resides in his/her heart". There are numerous poetic or metaphysical ways of describing this.

Kizza (2007) believes that social, moral, spiritual and cultural development is concerned with the ideas, beliefs and values. Spiritual development involves development of values, principles and beliefs which may or may not be religious and understanding the beliefs of others, experiencing a sense of awe, wonder and mystery, opportunities to reflect on life's fundamental questions and a search for meaning and purpose, development of spirit, soul, personality and character, valuing a non-material dimensions to life and appreciating the intangible, attributing meaning to experience, using feelings and emotions as a source of growth, recognizing the worth of others and gaining the ability to build up relationship with others and expressing and feeling through a creative outlet.

Moral development involves knowledge and understanding of society's shared and agreed values and moral codes and an awareness that these can change over time, opportunities to debate moral issues and a willingness to express views on ethical/moral issues and personal values, the confidence to act in accordance with one's principles, development of the ability to make responsible and reasoned judgments on moral dilemmas and think through consequence of actions, demonstrating respect for property and the environment and for other's needs, interests and feelings, being able to articulate attitudes and values and recognizing the oral dimensions to situations.

Social development involves of skills and personal qualities necessary for playing and effective role in society and also those inter-personal skills essential for successful for relationships, understanding of the institutions, structures and processes of society, understanding that what is learnt in the curriculum relates to life in society, relating to others and learning to work successfully as part of different teams, embracing contacts with society at different levels and participating in activities relevant to the community, development of the ability to adjust to a range of social contexts, appreciating the rights and responsibilities of individuals and exercising own responsibility, resolving conflicts and countering those things which threaten inclusion and unity.

Cultural development involves understanding personal culture as well as other cultures at a local, regional, national and global level, appreciation of and respect for cultural diversity, knowledge of the historical development of culture particularly processes and events which have shaped cultures, understanding that culture are evolving and changing and knowing how to cope with that change, feeling comfortable with emerging world culture linked to ICT and transport improvements and growing influence of media, appreciating interdependence of cultures, encountering a breath of stimuli from a range of cultures including music, art and literature, and an openness to new ideas and willingness to modify cultural values as appropriate.

Related Studies

Cruz (2010) conducted a study on Values Clarification of the Public Secondary Schools in Pangasinan I. She found out that the values of the students are influenced much by the home

and peers. There are factors considered as the guiding principles to strengthen the values of the students such as the church for the spirituality and morality of their action. The church according to the findings of Cruz is very influential in shaping the spiritual values of the students by joining the different spiritual activities they are able to acquire the values of respect, love, justice, peace and charity.

Delos Reyes (2011) conducted a study on shaping the values of the students by the Home and the School. She found out that the home and the school contribute much in the development and enhancement of the values of the students. The intervention of the home is necessary to follow up the values taught in school. The conclusion of Delos Reyes is that broken homes' lack of care and concern, love and respect in the family affect greatly the formation of values of students.

Another study on Core Values of students was conducted by Dr. De Guzman in the Public Secondary Students in Dagupan City. He found out that the leading core values are respect, justice and charity. These are valued very much by the students in establishing relationship with others. The home plays a vital role in establishing the foundation of the core values of the children and will determine their behavior in the society where they live.

In another work entitled: "The Basic Education Curriculum in 17 Easy Lessons", Values Education, according to Isagani R. Cruz, former Philippine Department of Education Undersecretary, is also a case of values transmission/inculcation. Cruz (2003) reminds the stakeholders in education that Filipino, English, Mathematics and Science are simple linguistic instruments for advancing one's learning in different areas of interest. Mastering all these tool subjects will not suffice in order to count one as an educated person.

The expression "Values Across the Curriculum" in BEC is an indication that the teaching of tool subjects includes Values Education (Cruz, 2003). Values Education as conceived here is likewise an instrument whose purpose is to get the students to imbibe pre-selected values. The slogan of the DepEd says it all: "Bawat graduate, bayani at marangal". [Every graduate, a hero and is honorable]. Broken down into specific values taught in Values Education, this slogan means that every product of the public school system will be "makabayan, makatao, makakalikasan, at maka-Diyos" (Cruz, 2003)

In a book titled Values Education, aside from teaching personal development, Bacungan, et.al. (2006) attempt to pass on the students certain values. Inculcation and conditioning are among the forms of teaching that were considered by the authors. They were not highly critical, however, about such non-reflective ways of effecting values acquisition. The discussion on Filipino spirituality and religiosity is basically inspired by Christian faith. Though other religions were mentioned, only a meager space was allotted for the discussion of their potential contributions to one's values or moral education. In sum, while the authors find the role of reflective thinking in Values Education honorable, the latter part of their work seems to show that Values Education is likewise a case of values transmission/inculcation.

The research of De Leon (2005) on Values of First and Fourth Year High School Students is another work that reflects the view that Values Education is a case of values transmission/inculcation. De Leon was particularly concerned with the relationship between the values of first and fourth year high school students selected Christian schools in the Philippines and the values of family, school, and society. To answer his other problems, he included teachers, school administrators, parents, and other members of society in his survey. De Leon found that there were significant differences in the values of all respondents with respect to seven (7) value

areas, namely: 1) unity and order; 2) knowledge and truth; 3) sense of others/fellowship; 4) justice; 5) art and beauty; 6) freedom, and 7) sense of God. Evidence further led De Leon (2005) to the observation that family, school, and societal values have significant separate influences on the values of the student.

De Leon (2005) in his study on Values Integration in Teaching Academic subjects suggested that educational endeavors can only be meaningful if they are pursued with the vision of attaining and cultivating certain universal values such as the one enumerated above. De Leon recommended the integration of the seven values in academic situation. “Values must be taught systematically” and “contained in the ‘hidden curriculum’ as exemplified by the teachers, staff, administrators and personnel of the schools”.

In the restructured curriculum from Grade 1 up to Fourth Year, the learner ought to have developed and internalized a value system that makes him/her a person of integrity who has the competence and courage to face contemporary challenges and has the firm commitment to serve his/her country, show respect for peoples and cultures, manifest care for the environment, and live with gratitude to the Creator” (2002 BEC pg.18)

That needs a lot of unpacking. Involved is a value system. Among the values included are those of patriotism (bayani) and honor (marangal). In addition there are other values that can be manifested like respect for self (paggalang sa sarili), a positive attitude towards work (positibong saloobin sa paggawa), knowledge and skill in livelihood and technology (kaalaman at kasanayan sa kabuhayan at teknolohiya), productivity (produktibo), appreciation for sports and dancing (pagpapahalaga sa sports at sayaw), respectful for culture (pagpapahalaga sa kultura), possession of a global vision (may global na pananaw), care for environment (pangangalaga sa kapaligiran), faithful in accomplishing one’s duty (pagtupad sa tungkulin), respectful of human rights (paggalang sa karapatang pantao), love of country (pagmamahal sa bansa).

The learner ought to have developed his/her value system. He/She also ought to have “internalized” it. This means that it is not just force on the students by way of rote or external disciplinary measures, as one trains a dog to sit when one say’s “Sit!” or to “shake hands” when one extends one’s hand, through a form of thoughtless Pavlovian conditioning. The system should present the value over and against other competing values, and the student should be invited to accept the value based on personal insight and free choice. The student chooses to care for the environment not because one will be punished for littering but because the values of the environment.

Escaño (2009) conducted a study on values integration in the teaching of sports. His findings reveals that the most emphasized values being integrated in sports are sportsmanship, fairness and honesty. These values according to his findings are influenced very much by the kind of teaching the teacher has and the example he sets for the students to follow particularly in playing the different sports and games.

Sison (2008) conducted a research on the Intellectual values of students. His findings showed that students must learn how to think critically in addressing evaluative, especially moral issues/dilemmas/controversies (e.g., abortion, death penalty, cloning, animal rights, and divorce). Teaching the students the rational approach to evaluative problems is getting them to learn the habit of clear thinking, gauging, and revising arguments, and using principles of good reasoning. He recommended that students must learn how to question – theirs and others – a position, theory, conviction, view, attitude, or belief that may either be grounded in faulty or cogent reasoning. Having the ability to think logically and independently paves the way to becoming a

person who values accountability. Students should learn to evaluate their reasoning abilities, styles and content of ideas.

Jose (2009) wrote a masteral thesis on Socio-Economic Values of high school students in Cordillera Region. He found out that among the economic practiced by the students, the value of time is the least practiced of while saving or budgeting is the most observed, recommended that proper training of students on economic values like resourcefulness, and budgeting should be given to students in subjects like technology and livelihood education.

With the vision of curing what is believed to be a socially ill Philippine society, former Philippine senator Leticia Ramos Shahani launched in 1987 a values training project called Moral Recovery Program (MRP). Shahani, however, admitted later that the program failed in its mission to change the Philippine society. In her work titled A Values Handbook of the Moral Recovery Program, she exhorted the teachers of Values Education to emphasize the promotion of harmony and social change. One of her aims is to lessen, if not entirely eliminate, the many enduring social problems (e.g., corruption in the government, colonial mentality) that beset the Filipino people, Shahani started with the enumeration of perceived strengths and weaknesses of the Filipino.

Family orientation, hard work and industry, and faith and religiosity were among those counted as Filipino assets. Extreme personalism, lack of discipline, and colonialism were cited as examples of their shared liabilities. Shahani said that some of the factors that explain the Filipino people's strengths and weaknesses are their home environment, history, religion, and mass media. She said that Filipinos should lay emphasis on the importance of valuing their country, collective interest, moral uprightness, discipline and so on. Shahani suggested, too, that every Filipino must aim to turn out students who are "maka-Diyos, makabansa, maka-kalikasan, at makatao" (roughly, they respectively mean: godly or devoted to one's accepted god, patriotic, pro-environment or environmentalist, and humanistic). To mold every student into a person the MRP wants him/her to be, Shahani recommended the use of the so-called experiential approach to learning values. Values Education here is aimed at endorsing certain values that must be imbibed by every student so that they behave according to the demands of the same.

In the hidden curriculum Miande and Echano (2005) identified some of the values which are expected to already be integrated in the BEC program. However, many are not clearly evident in teaching subjects where academic competency is more favorable than values formation.

Chapter 2

Research Methodology

This chapter presents the research design, locale and population of the study, data gathering tool, data gathering procedures, treatment of the data and statistical tools used in the study.

Research Design

The study used the descriptive type of research. According to Traverse (2000) descriptive method describes the nature of situation as it exists at the time of the study. Day (2001) defines it as an activity involving collection of data in order to test the hypothesis or to answer questions concerning the current status of the study.

Descriptive method of research used in this study because it attempted to analyze, interpret, and report the present extent of practice the of the fourth year high school students their values along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions.

It is the most appropriate type of research used in this study because it attempted to analyze, interpret, and report the present status of the manifestation of values of the fourth year high school values along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions, the dominant and less dominant values and the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered in the manifestation of said values.

Locale and Population of the Study

The study was conducted in the public secondary school n General Emilio Aguinaldo National High School with a total number of 304 teachers taken in complete enumeration.

Data Gathering Instrument

The data needed to answer the specific problems of the study was gathered through a questionnaire composed of two parts:

Part I. Extent of manifestation of the values of teachers.

Part II. Seriousness of problems encountered by the teachers in the manifestation of values of the fourth year students adopted this instrument, states the name of the author, the title of the thesis or dissertation. The instrument was adopted from the study of Daisy Ico entitled Values Manifested by High School Teacher in Public Secondary Schools in General Emilio Aguinaldo National High School.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the researcher administered the questionnaire he asked permission first from the Schools Division Superintendent. He also asked permission from the principal of the public secondary schools covered in his study. When permission was granted he started floating the questionnaire personally with the help of some teachers who are his close friends. In order to have one hundred percent retrieval of the instrument he patiently went to the school to collect them. It took him almost one month to administer and retrieve them due to the intervening

activities in the school that cause the delay for administration and collection of the instrument.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Gathered data were treated with the appropriate statistical techniques to answer specific questions or problems of this research.

For problem number 1, on the extent of values manifested by the teachers, average weighted means and the 3-value likert scale with their scale range and descriptive equivalents were used.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
3	2.34 – 3.00	High Extent
2	1.67 – 2.33	Moderate Extent
1	1.00 – 1.66	Low Extent

For problem number 2, to determine the significant differences, t-test was used with 2 variables. The formula is

Formula:

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{SD\bar{x}}$$

Where:

\bar{X}_1 = First Mean

\bar{X}_2 = Second Mean

$SD\bar{x}$ = Standard error of difference between the two means

For problem number 3 on the dominant and less dominant values, the limit that falls from 2.34 and above are the dominant values, 2.33 and below are the less dominant values.

For problem number 4 on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered the average weighted means, 3 Likert scale limits and descriptive equivalents were used.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating
3	2.34 – 3.00	Serious
2	1.67 – 2.33	Moderate Serious
1	1.00 – 1.66	Not Serious

Chapter 3

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

This chapter presents, analysis and interprets the data gathered in the light of the problems presented.

Extent of Manifestation of Values

The tables that follow present the extent of manifestation of the values of the teacher along the four dimensions namely, intellectual, social, spiritual and economic.

Intellectual Values

Table 2 presents the extent of manifestation of values along intellectual dimension.

Table 2

Extent of Manifestation of Values Teachers Along Intellectual Dimensions

Intellectual Values	Values of Teachers	
	WM	DE
1. Intellectual Courage	2.10	ME
2. Intellectual Empathy	1.70	ME
3. Intellectual Autonomy	1.51	LE
4. Intellectual Integrity	2.25	ME
5. Confidence in reasons	1.75	ME
6. Fairmindedness	1.58	LE
7. Critical Thinking	1.81	ME
8. Respect for opinion of others	1.59	LE
9. Ability to reason / analysis	1.66	LE
10. Accepting measuring from others	1.63	LE
Total Average Weighted Mean	1.76	ME

The table shows the perception of teachers. Based on the combined perceptions, there are five (5) out of ten (10) intellectual values which are moderately manifested. These are: intellectual integrity (2.25), intellectual coverage, (2.10), critical thinking (1.81), confidence in reason (1.75) and intellectual empathy (1.70).

Intellectual integrity means the recognition of the need to be true to one's own thinking

and to hold oneself to the same teachers one expects others to meet. Intellectual coverage refers to the willingness to grapple with difficult or confusing concepts. Critical thinking means the ability to think clearly and rationally above what to do and what to believe. Confidence in reason entails the recognition that good reasoning has its worth/value. Intellectual empathy involves the awareness of the need to put oneself in the place of others and to reason from premises, assumptions and ideas other than one's own.

The findings as stated reveal that teachers already manifest the intellectual traits which are indications of intellectual maturity.

There are, however, also five (5), out of 10 intellectual values which are lowly manifested. These are: intellectual autonomy (1.51), fair-mindedness (1.58), respect for opinion of others (1.59), ability to reason (1.66) and accepting measuring from others (1.63).

This means that the teachers still lack the ability to think for themselves (intellectual autonomy), make judgments free discrimination (fair-mindedness), respect the opinion of others, ability to analyze and accept measuring from others. These findings indicate that teachers have not yet internalized their values.

A further look at the table show that while there is an equal number of intellectual values rated as moderately manifested and lowly manifested, the overall extent of manifestation of values as perceived by the teachers themselves (1.73) is moderately manifested respectively. An overall weighted mean of 1.76 indicates that the extent of manifestation of the intellectual values of teachers is moderate.

This means that as a whole the teachers already manifest to a certain degree values traits necessary for right action and correct thinking.

Social Values

Table 3 presents the extent of manifestation of social values of teachers.

The perception of teachers show that three (3) out of the ten (10) social values are highly manifested. These are: cleanliness (2.75), communication (2.79) and friendship (2.43).

Table 3

Extent of Manifestation Along the Social Values

Social Values	Values of Teachers	
	WM	DE
1. Cooperation	2.14	ME
2. Admiration	2.16	ME
3. Cleanliness	2.75	HE
4. Communication	2.79	HE

5. Conformity	1.85	ME
6. Friendship	2.43	HE
7. Honesty	2.09	ME
8. Happiness	1.78	ME
9. Self-reliance	1.48	LE
10. Sincerity	2.0	ME
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.15	ME

The highest among the three (3) is communication (2.79). This means that the imparting or exchange of information or news is a behavior teacher manifest or practice all the time. In fact much of the activities of teachers is devoted to communication. Thus, it is not a surprise that it is the social value which has the higher extent of manifestation. Communication is followed by cleanliness (2.75). This implies that students appreciate and recognize the importance of an environment that free from waste, dirt, dust, stains, bad smell and the like. A clean environment promotes hygiene and the health of the people in the community.

Friendship is the third social value that is highly manifested by teachers (2.43) with their peers and people around them. This is a normal phenomenon since man, by nature, is a social being.

The table also shows that there are six (6) social values which are moderately manifested. They are: cooperation (2.14), admiration (2.16), conformity (1.85), honesty (2.09), happiness (1.78) are sincerity (2.0).

Cooperation means the ability of working together to the same end or engaging in mutually beneficial activities. Admiration is the feeling of wonder, pleasure, warm approval or respect for a worthwhile achievement. Conformity is compliance with standards, rules or laws. Honesty implies uprightness of character and action. It entails the refuse to lie, steal, or deceive or do any wrong. Happiness is the ability to exhibit a positive or pleasant emotion ranging from contentment to intense joy. Sincerity is being free from posturize, decent of happening.

The findings that these values are only moderately manifested means that teachers have not yet fully realized and internalized the values that can enable them to work in harmony with and related well with people.

Finally table 3 reveals that there is one (1) social value that is lowly manifested. It is self-reliance (1.48). This means that teachers do not have the ability to depend on their own capability, judgment or resources.

An overall analysis of the findings in table 3 reveal that there are three (3) values which are highly manifested, six (6) values which are moderately manifested and one (1) values which is lowly manifested. Taking the overall weighted mean, however, indicates that the trackers (2.17) and the teachers (2.12) gave an overall extent of manifestation as moderate (2.15).

This means that while there are varieties in the extent of manifestation of social values, it can be said that, as a whole, the teachers have shown capabilities that can contribute to the stability of the social order and provide guidelines for social conduct.

Spiritual Values

The table presents the extent of manifestation of spiritual values.

The perception of teachers reveal that there are two (2), out of the ten (10) spiritual values which are highly manifested. They are fourth (2.85) are forgiving / compassion (2.86).

These imply that the teachers manifest traits of confidence or trust in a person or a supreme being and guidelines of feelings of deep sympathy and sorrow for another who is stricken by misfortune.

The table also shows that, there are eight (8) spiritual values which are moderately manifested. They are: mercy (2.14), truthfulness (2.16), self-grooving (2.08), generosity/charity (1.78), gratitude (1.94), justice (1.79), peace (1.98) and sacrifice (1.90).

This means that values which foster a kind, forgiving treatment of someone who could be treated heartily (mercy), telling or imposing the truth (truthfulness), are being kind of generous (generosity/charity) are not fully appreciated by the teacher.

Table 4

Extent of Manifestation of Fourth Year Students Along Spiritual Values

Spiritual Values	Teachers		Students		Overall	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Mercy	2.10	ME	2.18	ME	2.14	ME
2. Truthfulness	2.12	ME	2.20	ME	2.16	ME
3. Self-growing	2.10	ME	2.05	ME	2.08	ME
4. Faith	2.80	HE	2.90	HE	2.85	HE
5. Forgiving/Compassion	2.83	HE	2.89	HE	2.86	HE
6. Generosity/Charity	1.81	ME	1.75	ME	1.78	ME
7. Gratitude	2.0	ME	1.88	ME	1.94	ME
8. Justice	1.75	ME	1.83	ME	1.79	ME
9. Peace	1.95	ME	2.01	ME	1.98	ME
10. Sacrifice	1.85	ME	1.96	ME	1.90	ME
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.13	ME	2.17	ME	2.15	ME

Similarly, it is also evident that teachers have not yet fully internalized behaviors that manifest reliance or self (self-growing), thankfulness or readiness to show appreciation for acts of kindness (gratitude), the ability to give what is due (justice), the readiness to free disturbance or act of giving up something that he/she wants to keep (sacrifice).

Taken as a whole, the extent of manifestation of spiritual values as perceived by teachers is moderate. This means that teachers have not yet recognize and internalized fully values that foster connectedness to the divine or spiritual dimensions of human experience.

Economic Values

Table 5 presents the extent of manifestation economic values.

Table 5
Extent of Manifestation of Fourth Year Students

Economic Values	Teachers		School Administrator		Overall	
	AW M	DE	AWM	DE	AW M	DE
1. Thrift	2.95	HE	2.50	HE	2.73	HE
2. Quality of choices on goods etc. products.	1.75	ME	2.65	ME	2.20	ME
3. Value of time	2.10	ME	2.80	ME	2.45	ME
4. Saving / Budgeting	1.50	LE	1.60	LE	1.55	LE
5. Willingness to pay on obligation	1.60	ME	1.75	ME	1.78	ME
6. Conservative in buying things	1.85	ME	1.81	ME	1.83	ME
7. Spending within means	1.90	ME	1.82	ME	1.86	ME
8. Giving up in other goals.	1.69	ME	1.72	ME	1.71	ME
9. Hardwork	2.60	HE	2.75	HE	2.68	HE
10. Resourceful	2.65	HE	2.70	HE	2.68	HE
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.08	ME	2.21	ME	2.15	ME

As shown in the table, the combined perceptions of teachers reveal that there are four economic values which are highly manifested. They are thrift (2.73), value of time (2.45), hardwork (2.68) and resourcefulness (2.65).

This means that the teachers have fully appreciated the values of the careful use of

money so that it is not wasted (thrift), the value of time spent on a given activity (value of time) the need to apply their ability with focus and intensify to the exclusion of others possibilities (hard work) and creativity to cope with difficulties (resourcefulness). The same table shows that there are five (5) economic values which are moderately manifested. They are: quality of choices on goods, products (2.20) willingness to pay obligation (1.78) conservative in buying things (1.81), spending within means (1.86) and giving up on other goods (1.71).

The findings imply that teachers, although they realized the significance of these values, they do not yet practice or manifest these often.

Finally, as also shown in the table that there is one (1) value that is lowly manifested. It is saving/budgeting (1.55). This means teachers have not yet acquired the value of making conscious decision about how they prefer to allocate their money.

A find look at the table reveals that the overall weighted means of the extent of manifestation of economic values is 2.15. This means, that as a whole, the extent of manifestation of economic values is moderate. This means that the teachers do not yet fully realize and practice the tools and resources they have relative to the production consumption and transfer of wealth.

Summary of Perception of Teachers on the Manifestation of Values Along the Four Dimensions

Table 6 presents the summary of the perceptions along the four dimensions.

Table 6
Summary of Perceptions of Teachers on the Manifestation of Values
Along the Four Dimensions

Values Manifested	TEACHERS	
	WM	DE
1. Intellectual	1.77	ME
2. Social	2.15	ME
3. Spiritual	2.15	ME
4. Economic	2.15	ME
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.05	ME

The extent of manifestation of the values teachers along the four dimensions is moderate. This implies, that as a whole the values along the four dimensions are not yet fully appreciated, internalized and practiced by the teachers.

It is noted, however, that among the four dimensions, the intellectual values have the lowest weighted mean. This means that the intellectual values are not as much manifested as the other three (3) which are all given the same average weighted means.

Dominant and Less Dominant Values

The tables that follows the dominant and less dominant values manifested by the teachers.

Table 7

Dominant and Less Dominant Values of Teachers Along Intellectual Dimensions

Intellectual Values	Dominant		Less Dominant	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
1. Intellectual Courage			2.10	ME
2. Intellectual Empathy			1.70	ME
3. Intellectual Autonomy			1.51	LE
4. Intellectual Integrity			2.25	ME
5. Confidence in reasons			1.75	ME
6. Fairmindedness			1.58	LE
7. Critical Thinking			1.81	ME
8. Respect for opinion of others			1.59	LE
9. Ability to reason / analysis			1.66	LE
10. Accepting measuring from others			1.63	LE
Total Average Weighted Mean			2.05	ME

It could be noted that there are no dominant intellectual values to the teachers. This means that none of them are fully manifested, internalized, and practiced.

The situation is made worse by the fact that several dimensions of intellectual development such as autonomy, fairminded, respect for opinion of others, ability to reason out, accept measuring from others are not at all developed.

This means that the teachers development along intellectual dimensions needs to be enhanced further.

Table 8

Dominant and Less Dominant Values of Teachers Along Social Dimension

Social Values	Dominant		Less Dominant	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
1. Cooperation			2.14	ME
2. Admiration			2.16	ME
3. Cleanliness	2.75	HE		
4. Communication	2.75	HE		
5. Conformity			1.85	ME
6. Friendship	2.43	HE		
7. Honesty			2.09	ME
8. Happiness			1.78	ME
9. Self-reliance			1.48	LE
10. Sincerity			2.0	ME
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.64	HE	1.93	ME

The table shows that there are three (3) dominant social values of teachers. They are cleanliness, communication and friendship. This means these are values that are fully internalized and practiced by teachers.

All the other social values are not yet fully developed and therefore, are in need of further reinforcement, special attention should be given to the social value of self-reliance since it is least developed of all the social values.

Table 9
Dominant and Less Dominant Values of Teachers
Along Spiritual Dimensions

Spiritual Values	Dominant		Less Dominant	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
1. Mercy			2.14	ME
2. Truthfulness			2.16	ME
3. Self-growing			2.08	ME
4. Faith	2.85	HE		
5. Forgiving/Compassion	2.86	HE		
6. Generosity/Charity			1.78	ME
7. Gratitude			1.94	ME
8. Justice			1.79	ME
9. Peace			1.98	ME
10. Sacrifice			1.90	ME
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.86	HE	1.97	ME

It could be noted that there are two (2) dominant spiritual values of teachers. These are faith and forgiving/compassion. This means they manifest and practice their values to the fullest.

All the others are less dominant values and therefore are not fully internalized and practiced. As such, there is a need to provide opportunities for their further development and enhancement.

Table 10
Dominant and Less Dominant Values of Fourth Year Students

Economic Values	Dominant		Less Dominant	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
1. Thrift	2.73	HE		
2. Quality of choices on goods etc. products.			2.20	ME
3. Value of time	2.45	HE		

4. Saving / Budgeting			1.55	ME
5. Willingness to pay on obligation			1.78	ME
6. Conservative in buying things			1.85	ME
7. Spending within means			1.86	ME
8. Giving up in other goals.			1.71	ME
9. Hardwork	2.68	HE		
10. Resourceful	2.68	HE		
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.63	HE	1.82	ME

It is shown in the table that the four (4) dominant economic values of teachers are thrift value of time, hard work and resourcefulness. These means these are the values that are fully internalized and practiced.

All the others are less dominant and therefore are in need of further development and enhancement. Savings/budgeting must be given special attention since it is the economic value that is lesser development and manifested.

Problems Encountered in the Manifestation of Values

Intellectual Values

Table 11 presents the problems along intellectual values.

Table 11

Problems Encountered by the Respondents Along Intellectual Values

Values	Teachers		Students		Overall		Rank
	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	
1. Lack of intellectual courage	2.33	S	2.40	S	2.37	S	3
2. Poor intellectual empathy to others	2.20	MS	2.30	MS	2.25	MS	4
3. Lack of intellectual honesty	2.10	MS	2.15	MS	2.13	MS	5
4. Poor orientation of intellectual development	2.40	S	2.35	S	2.38	S	2
5. Low ability to analyze and respect the opinion of	2.39	S	2.40	S	2.40	S	1

others.							
Total Average Weighted Mean	2.28	MS	2.32	MS	2.3	MS	

It could be noted that the serious problems that confront students in the development of intellectual values are low ability to analyze and respect the opinion of others (2.40), poor orientation on intellectual development (2.38) and lack of intellectual courage.

This means students have not yet acquired the ability to think critically, be tolerant of opinion of others and to face or grapple with difficult or confusing concepts.

Social Values

Table 12 presents the problems met by the respondents along social values.

Table 12
Problems Encountered by the Respondents Along Social Values

B. Social Values	Teachers		Rank
	AW M	DE	
1. Poor spirit of cooperation and collaboration.	1.68	MS	4
2. Lack of conformity with the norms of society.	2.10	MS	1
3. Poor communication barriers	1.61	NS	5
4. Disunity, dishonesty in dealing with some organization	1.69	MS	3
5. Decisiveness of culture and diversity of opinion.	1.70	MS	2
Total Average Weighted Mean	1.76	MS	

The table reveals that students do not have serious problems in the development of social values. As such, they can easily cope with difficulties that come their way. However, it could be noted that there are certain situations such as lack of conformity with the norms of society, divisiveness of culture and diversity of opinion and discernity or dishonesty in dealing with some organization that need to be addressed. Teachers need to be trained along areas such as complying with social norms and living in harmony with all the people they come in contact with.

Spirit Values

Table 13 presents the problems encountered by the respondents along spiritual values.

Table 13

Problems Encountered by the Respondents Along Spiritual Values

N=293 Teachers

342 Students

C. Spiritual Values	Teachers		Rank
	AW M	DE	
1. Religious conflict of worship and doctrine	1.58	NS	4
2. Lack of respect for one's religions	1.59	NS	3
3. Lack of mercy and compassion with the situation of others	1.69	MS	2
4. Inability to practice charity and generosity	1.71	MS	1
5. Weak faith and spiritual sacrifice	1.50	NS	5

Based on the data presented in the table, students do not seem to have problems that they cannot readily overcome. Most of the problems they encounter are not serious. However, they should learn to develop further values on mercy and compassion as well as charity and generosity.

Economic Values

Table 14 presents the problems encountered by the respondents along economic values.

It is evident from the table that all the problems the students encountered along economic values are serious. This means that if they are not resolved or addressed properly, they can adversely affect the development of the economic values of students.

Table 14

Problems Encountered by the Respondents Along Economic Values

N = 239

342 Students

D. Economic Values	Teachers		Rank
	AW M	DE	
1. Extravagant speaking	2.76	S	4
2. Inability to budget time and money (allowance)	2.88	S	1

3. Lack of resourcefulness	2.68	S	5
4. Inability to practice charity and generosity	2.84	S	2
5. Lack of training on economic aspect of life's actively (thrift)	2.77	S	3

An analysis of the problems show that the problems encountered by students revolved around their inability to utilize the tools and resources they have at their disposal to insure that economic activities they engage in attaining the goals they intend to achieve.

PROPOSED PLAN OF ACTION

The proposed plan of action in intended to improve/enhance the extent of the manifestation of values by the teachers of public secondary teachers, Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo.

Focus is given to the problems encountered in manifestation of the values along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic values as well as the less dominant manifestation of the said value.

The proposed program has the following components:

- a. Areas of Concern
- b. Objectives / Targets
- c. Activities / Strategies
- d. Persons Involved
- e. Budget Estimate
- f. Time frame
- g. Success Indicator

Proposed Plan of Action to Improve / Enhance the Manifestation of Values by the Teachers

Areas of Concern	Targets / Objectives	Activities / Strategies	Persons / Agencies Involved	Budget	Time Frame	Success Indicator
A. Intellectual Values 1. Intellectual Autonomy	Cultivate in the students independence thinking/and self-intellectual development	1. Giving the students research activity containing critical questions. 2. Activities on intellectual self-reliance e.g. solving some problems, puzzle.	Students, teachers, guidance counselor, administrators, values education, teachers, parents.	P10,000	Weekly or if it is necessary during class hours	90 percent of the teachers shall have developed intellectual autonomy.
2. Fair-mindedness	Acquire value son intellectual honesty and fairness sports.	1. Activities on bibliographic entries in research. 2. Group work and identification of the contributors and the source of chess and reports of references.	Teachers, students, librarian, guidance counselor, parent school administration.	P10,000	Weekly or as scheduled in the class or as a part of class activities.	90 percent of the teachers shall have acquired the values of fair-mindedness
B. Social Values 1. Self-reliance / sacrifice	Practice the values of self-reliance / sacrifice.	Values training and clarification activities. Group work to inform field work	Teachers / values educated conductive students /	P15,000	Every week / or as needed class	90 percent of the teachers shall have developed

		survey. Dramatization activities.	principals, parents, guests, sponsors		hours	values of self reliance / sacrifice
2. Conformity	Learn how to agree / confirm with fellow beings / peer, groups, etc.	1. Activities in the class or conformity. 2. Debate / agree or disagree 3. Giving of opinion activity 4. Dramatization	Students / teachers, facilitators, administrators, sponsorship, guest, etc.	P10,000	Class hours, weekly, monthly / and or as scheduled	90 percent of the teachers shall have acquired or attended activities on conformity values formation.
C. Spiritual Values 1. Justice	Practice the value of jurisdiction in life like respecting other's religions.	Simulation activities. Questions for justice manifestation. Discussion Seminar as values along justice / fairness honesty.	Students, teachers, lecturers, guests principals / sponsorship	P15,000	As scheduled every end to the semester of the year.	90 percent of the teachers shall have acquired and developed the values on spiritual.
D. Economic Values 1. Savings / Budget	Practice the values of savings / budgeting	1. Lecture on values of savings. 2. Group dynamics on "tipid" program. 3. Seminar on economic	Students / teachers / parents, community.	P5,000	Daily follow up of activities – week, monthly, variety reportin	90 percent of the teachers shall have savings activity / report.

		values.			g	
2. Reso urceful- ness	Practice the values of resourcefuln ess	1. Lecture on resourcefuln ess 2. Seminar on values of resourcefuln ess. 3. Entrepre neurial activities	Students / teachers, parents, community, sponsorship	P10,00 0	Monthly Quarterl y	90 percent of the teachers shall have acquired the values of resourcefuln ess

Chapter 4

Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendation

This chapter presents the summary of salient findings, conclusions and recommendation.

Summary

This study determined the extent of manifestation of values of the teachers in public secondary schools in Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo Public Secondary Schools, Cavite City along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions. It also looked into the dominant and less dominant value as well as the problems encountered in the manifestation of the above-stated value.

Findings

The following are the salient findings of the study:

1. The extent of manifestation of the values of teachers is moderate along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions.
2. There is no significant differences between the perceptions of teachers and students in the effect of manifestation of values of fourth year students.
3. The dominant and less dominant values manifested are as follows:
 - 3.1 There are no dominant intellectual values, all are less dominant
 - 3.2 Two spiritual values, namely, fourth and forging/compassion are dominant. All the others are less dominant.
 - 3.3 Four (4) economic values, namely, thrift, value of time, hardwork are resourcefulness, are dominant all the other are less dominant.
 - 3.4 Four (4) economics values, namely thrift, value of time, hardwork and resourcefulness are dominant all the others are less dominant.
4. The degree of seriousness of problems encountered is:
 - 4.1 Moderate along intellectual values
 - 4.2 Moderate along social values
 - 4.3 Not serious along spiritual values
 - 4.4 Serious along economic values
5. A plan of action to enhance the manifestation of values of teachers has been proposed.

Conclusion

The conclusion based on the findings of the study are as follows:

1. Most of the values along intellectual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions are not yet

fully internalized and put into produce by teacher.

2. Both students and teachers have the same perceptions on the extent of manifestation of values of teachers.
3. Most of the values along the individual, social, spiritual and economic dimensions are not fully evident in the behavior and conduct of teachers.
4. The seriousness of the problems hampers the manifestation of the values of teachers along all dimensions.
5. A proposed plan the enhance the manifestation and internalization of values of teacher has been formulated.

Recommendation

The following recommendation based on the findings and conclusions are herewith forwarded:

1. The proposed plan of action shall be endorsed to the schools division Superintendent of Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo, Cavite for consideration and adaptation.
2. Further research on values of students shall be undertaken by other researcher.

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